

TRAINING AND SKILLS DEVELOPMENT FOR SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETERS

Xasanova Xilola Ikrom qizi

UzSWLU, third year student

Abstract. Simultaneous interpretation is a demanding profession that requires a unique set of skill and extensive training. Interpreters must be able to listen, comprehend, translate and speak almost at the same time. This process necessitates exceptional cognitive abilities and language proficiency. This article delve into the necessary skills, training programs, and professional development opportunities available for aspiring simultaneous interpreters.

Keywords: Simultaneous interpretation, language skills, cultural knowledge, high profile case, split-second decisions, credibility, trust-developing connection.

Introduction. The simultaneous interpretation is a complex type. It is bilingual, sense-oriented.¹ There is a common belief that now, in the age of technology we don't have a need for human translators. We can manage with the help of machine translation tools, AI and etc. Then why we should hire an interpreter and pay him/her? However, people who have been in the spheres of language, translation claim that the world cannot reject human interpreters and translators. Because they see some clear reasons that others cannot. It is true that AI can even interpret oral speech as well, but is it able to understand the „human language“? Oral speech is not always that smooth, there may be some shortened forms of words or phrases, inversions, self-made metaphors, idioms that demand for a careful approach. Also, sometimes there is obvious rudeness or disrespect that

¹ Omon Muminov, A guide to simultaneous translation, Tashkent-2005

is usually better to be replaced with mildness and respect to prevent the potential contradiction. So I think the best way is to choose human for interpreting simultaneously, nevertheless it is okay to be assisted by AI.

Main part. Simultaneous interpretation is when the interpreter renders the speaker's meaning in one language to another in real time. Unlike consecutive interpretation where the interpreter waits for the speaker to make a pause before reformulating the message. This mode of interpretation is preferred for events that have multilingual participants such as webinars, conferences, meetings, court proceedings, and international broadcasts. Simultaneous interpreters do their job via these 3 possible steps:

- actively listen to the speaker;
- analyze and decode the message;
- produce an equivalent and culturally sensitive message.

How to become a simultaneous interpreter? That is the common question most people who are willing to work as a interpreter ask for. First of all, a bachelor's degree is usually needed to get this job. Many interpreters start with a degree in languages, linguistics or translation studies. These programs provide a strong foundation in language skills and cultural knowledge. Also, specialized master's degrees in conference interpreting or translation and interpretation are highly recommended. These programs offer advanced training in simultaneous interpretation techniques and practices. Even though it is not compulsory to be certified, it is recommended to study special certification programs to develop interpreter's skills and professionalism. These all increases the opportunity of being hired. Plus to the educational pathways above, some skills are also considered to have for pursuing a successful career as an interpreter:

1. Language proficiency. As a simultaneous interpreter, it is a must to have impeccable knowledge in one or more languages in addition to the native language. Just being bilingual cannot be enough, the understanding of that should be

comparable to an educated native speaker. He/She should be able to read the newspaper and understand the jokes in the comic section and converse about historical, theoretical, political, and social subject matter with ease.² It is imperative to be extremely articulate in your native language as well as in the foreign language.

2. Managing with stress. The ability to deal with stress well is a quality that is important to have as a simultaneous interpreter. At times the job can be very stressful, fast paced and tiring. That is an immense amount of responsibility to have on shoulder, especially if it is regarding a negatively charged political matter or a high profile court case.³ The interpreter has to keep up in pace and constantly be accurate throughout his/her interpretation. The focus has to be 100% during the process, not allowing the self to lose the attention.

3. Excellent listening and comprehension. Interpreters need to accurately grasp spoken words and the context in which they are used. This involves understanding different accents, dialects, and speech rates. They should know how to listen attentively to the speakers in order to understand the words accurately while also keeping track of the latest information and developments.

4. Cultural and linguistic understanding. Simultaneous interpreters need to have knowledge of both the culture and language of both the source and target languages. This can help them to comprehend and convey the cultural aspects, language nuance, and corresponding expressions during the interpreting process.

5. Quick and accurate decision-making. The ability to make split-second decisions is crucial. During the interpreting process simultaneous interpreters usually have more than one option in terms of words, idioms or other language units. If they cannot decide quickly they may miss the speech, and this not only makes them nervous but also causes to lose the point.

² G.V.Chernov, Theory and practice of simultaneous translation, 1978

³ Training, Cambridge Conference Interpreting Course (CCIC)

6. Strong public speaking skills. Clear and articulate delivery is essential, as interpreters often work in settings where their translations are heard by large audiences.⁴ Also, the tone, volume of speech should be taken into account to provide the audience with an appropriate and clear interpretation. These skills enhance the degree of credibility and a trust-developing connection. The end result is a more gratifying experience for the interpreter and a lasting memory in the minds of the people encountered.

7. High concentration and memory. Keeping focus for extended periods and retaining information briefly while translating is necessary for accuracy and consistency⁵. Sometimes sentences are too long or confusing to understand, and converting them into another language is not a piece of cake. However, experienced interpreters find the way to deal with them maybe by dividing the sentence into parts to deliver the whole meaning or by getting the gist and conveying only this. In cases alike memory is the best tool they need.

Having these skills helps to be an excellent interpreter.

Specialization in fields such as legal, medical or conference interpretation further enhances an interpreter's versatility and marketability. Specialized training programs and certifications enable interpreters to cater to specific industry needs, thereby expanding their professional opportunities and ensuring high standards of service in critical settings.

Conclusion. The path to becoming a proficient simultaneous interpreter is both demanding and rewarding marked by rigorous training and continuous professional growth. It requires more than just bilingual proficiency, demanding specialized training and the development of a comprehensive skill set. Through formal education, practical experience and continuous professional development, interpreters can achieve the high level of expertise needed to succeed in this

⁴ Sawyer, David B, Fundamental aspects of interpreter education: Curriculum and assessment, 2004

⁵ Po'chhacker, Franz, Introducing interpreting studies, 2016

challenging field. The investment in training and skills development is essential for those looking to excel in the dynamic world of simultaneous interpretation.

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